

The curve length of the ellipse

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We view an usual ellipse:

We need the canonical equation:

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} = 1$$

a and b are the semimajor and the semiminor axis. We transform to y^2 :

$$y^2 = b^2 \cdot \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}\right) = \frac{b^2}{a^2} \cdot (a^2 - x^2)$$

It follows:

$$y = \pm \frac{b}{a} \cdot \sqrt{a^2 - x^2}$$

We derive with the chain rule:

$$y'(x) = \pm \frac{b}{a} \cdot \frac{-x}{\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}}$$

Now we look at the following figure:

The arc length U_s can be expressed generally:

$$U_s = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + y'(x)^2} dx$$

Thus the arc length of the ellipse is:

$$U[x_1, x_2] = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + y'(x)^2} dx = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{1 + \frac{b^2}{a^2} \cdot \frac{x^2}{a^2 - x^2}} dx \quad (1)$$

We transform:

$$\begin{aligned} U[x_1, x_2] &= \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \sqrt{\frac{a^4 - a^2x^2 + b^2x^2}{a^2(a^2 - x^2)}} dx \\ &= \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \frac{\sqrt{a^2(a^2 - x^2) + b^2x^2}}{a\sqrt{a^2 - x^2}} dx \\ &= \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \frac{\sqrt{a^2 \cdot \left(\frac{a^2 - x^2}{a^2}\right) + \frac{b^2x^2}{a^2}}}{a \cdot \sqrt{\frac{a^2 - x^2}{a^2}}} dx \\ &= \int_{x_1}^{x_2} \frac{\sqrt{a^2 \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}\right) + \frac{b^2x^2}{a^2}}}{a \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}} dx \end{aligned}$$

We introduce the following substitution:

$$\frac{x}{a} = \cos t \quad \frac{x^2}{a^2} = \cos^2 t \quad 1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2} = \sin^2 t$$

It follows:

$$t = \arccos\left(\frac{x}{a}\right)$$

at last:

$$\frac{dt}{dx} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{a^2}}} \cdot \frac{1}{a} = \frac{-1}{\sin t} \cdot \frac{1}{a}$$

We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} U[x_1, x_2] &= \int_{\arccos\left(\frac{x_1}{a}\right)}^{\arccos\left(\frac{x_2}{a}\right)} - \frac{\sqrt{a^2 \sin^2 t + b^2 \cos^2 t}}{a \cdot \sin t} \cdot \sin t \cdot a dt \\ &= \int_{\arccos\left(\frac{x_1}{a}\right)}^{\arccos\left(\frac{x_2}{a}\right)} \sqrt{a^2 \sin^2 t + b^2 \cos^2 t} dt \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

This integral can be found in similar form at Barner [1] chapter 14.1,p.86.

Now we calculate numerical with $a=1$ and $b=0.8$ and with equation (1). We insert $x_1 = 0$ and $x_2 = h$. A special case is $h = 1$. In this case in equation (1) is a singularity that can be treated with equation (2).

This integral cannot be calculated exactly. We use the Gauss-Kronrod-method for numerical integration.

The result is presented in the following table:

h	$U[0, h]$
0.1	0.1001
0.2	0.2009
0.3	0.3030
0.4	0.4074
0.5	0.5153
0.6	0.6285
0.7	0.7499
0.8	0.8854
0.9	1.0508
0.91	1.0705
0.92	1.0912
0.93	1.1131
0.94	1.1365
0.95	1.1617
0.96	1.1894
0.97	1.2205
0.98	1.2572
0.99	1.3046
0.995	1.3380
0.999	1.3823
0.9999	1.4068
1.0000	1.4181

With $h = 1$ we get a quarter of the ellipse's perimeter. Thus the perimeter is $U=5.6724$ units of length.

References

- [1] Martin Barner, Friedrich Flohr "Analysis II" de Gruyter Verlag Berlin 1983